

GENDER EDUCATION AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Annotation. This article analyses the factors contributing to gender inequality in the education system, as well as the influence of gender stereotypes shaped by society's entrenched ideals of "man" and "woman." It highlights the causes of social stereotype formation, scientific and practical approaches to overcoming them, the development of educational materials on the subject, the importance of informing educators, and the necessity of creating equal opportunities and a safe environment for all, regardless of gender. The elimination of gender stereotypes in the education system and the creation of a balanced environment for equal use of opportunities for personal development are scientifically proven to contribute to the promotion of gender equality and the advancement of society.

Keywords: gender, equality, stereotypes, gender dimensions, women, family, society, education, politics, opportunities, development.

Introduction. Gender equality, one of the key priorities of Uzbekistan's policy, has remained relevant in all periods, much like issues of human rights and freedoms. Gender equality is one of the most important factors determining human progress and the future.

In ensuring the primacy of human rights and interests in Uzbekistan, gender equality is among the state's strategic directions. In the new Uzbekistan, the issue of gender equality is being implemented based on a new approach, fresh perspectives, and modern solutions. The relevance of this issue, regarded as a social policy priority, is reflected in the legal measures being undertaken to increase women's access to higher education and the privileges being created for women. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated: "If a girl receives an education, gains higher qualifications, and learns a modern profession, the atmosphere in the family will be completely different." [1]

Methodology and Research Methods. The methodological foundation of this research is based on the ideas and principles enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the goals outlined in the speeches of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, and the strategic tasks set out in the Development Strategy for the New Uzbekistan. This study employs the principles of scientific objectivity,

comparative analysis, logic, historicity, generality, specificity, induction, and deduction.

Main Body. “Gender” has historically been a socially relevant issue that has attracted the attention of leading thinkers, scholars, and philosophers of every era. The term “gender” was introduced into scientific discourse by American sociologist Robert Stoller. The term began to be used following his presentation on issues related to sex and gender at a congress held in Stockholm. He was the first to distinguish and scientifically define the concepts of biological sex and socio-cultural gender. [2]. Gender stereotypes refer to stable images, templates, models, social expectations, and behavioural sets that define forms of conduct, social roles, worldviews, ideologies, and emotional intelligence according to male/female dichotomies. [3] These are templates assigned to the images of “woman” and “man” that have been shaped and entrenched over centuries in a given society. Based on their biological sex, individuals act according to prevailing “femininity” and “masculinity” stereotypes. The activity patterns of individuals vary based on their unique characteristics. Social norms and roles tied to a given sex determine the direction of an individual’s socialisation. This process is shaped by the stereotypes, stable behavioural norms, and moral standards of the society in which the person lives. According to I.S. Klyosina, gender socialisation encompasses identification, gender schemes, social expectations and models, and sex-based roles. [4]. A person’s gender socialisation is influenced by their environment and social agents, continually shaped by gender-based social constructs. This is evident in social expectations that define boys as serious, authoritative, emotionally reserved, physically strong, and dutiful in military service, while girls are expected to be skilled in household chores, cooking, nimble, obedient, and destined to become wise wives and caring mothers.

As E.A. Karkishenko notes, based on findings from gender studies: “In the educational process, lessons conducted by teachers, career guidance activities, extracurricular specialised sessions, and daily interpersonal interactions among students are permeated with gender stereotypes. Teachers base the interaction of boys and girls on outdated stereotypes of male and female roles.” [5]. Analysis of literature dedicated to gender issues reveals that men are predominantly depicted as agents involved in economic, diplomatic, and military affairs, while women are portrayed as wives, social workers, caregivers, and similar roles. The analysis identifies three groups of gender stereotypes prevalent in education: stereotypes about psychological differences between students of different sexes

that significantly affect the learning process; stereotypes about the gender-specific interests and occupational preferences of men and women; and stereotypes about family roles – boys are prepared to be “breadwinners,” and girls to be nurturing wives or caregivers. [6]

Research indicates that gender factors play a key role in youth career choices. For instance, a study conducted in collaboration with UNICEF, the “Yuksalish” movement, and the Youth Union of Uzbekistan showed that most young people made choices based on deeply ingrained traditional perceptions. In terms of career interest, 8.1% of males and only 1.7% of females chose entrepreneurship; 14.5% of males and only 1.0% of females expressed interest in military careers. In contrast, 18.0% of females and 4.6% of males chose the medical profession. Nursing was chosen by 7.4% of females, while no males expressed interest in it. Teaching was selected by 24.4% of females and 7.2% of males; tailoring attracted 8.8% of females and only 0.2% of males. [7] These results demonstrate that gender plays a significant role in occupational choices.

The fact that university students – the respondents in the study – support revising traditional views suggests the potential for achieving gender equality. The higher level of support for revisiting stereotypes among respondents with university degrees indicates that higher education should become a key mechanism in implementing gender equality policies. “Mastering the fundamentals of gender studies aligns with the core goals of modernising higher education. In pedagogical practice, varied teaching methods based on egalitarian (non-stereotypical) approaches are essential to ensuring equal rights and opportunities,” says G. O‘razalieva. [8]

The rapid changes in social life demand that researchers adopt new approaches to the issue of gender asymmetry. One of the most pressing issues in the education system is the presence of gender stereotypes in textbooks. The language and terminology used in educational publications must be free of such biases and subjected to gender analysis.

Gender education is aimed at eliminating the unjust differentiation of social roles and their unequal status and positions by promoting skills to analyse social realities through the lens of individual experiences of men and women. [9] Thus, scientific research must develop neutral gender strategies to eliminate stereotypes from education. Considering the learner’s individual psychophysiological characteristics is key to their academic success. These traits determine how students perceive educational material and acquire knowledge, skills, and competencies. Existing stereotypical content in curricula can

encourage leadership and managerial ambitions in males while limiting the behavioural models accessible to females.

To eliminate gender stereotypes in the education system, the following are necessary:

- Limiting gendered “templates” in textbooks and analysing the content and language through gender expertise;
- Designing textbooks that support gender equality and provide an environment conducive to the development of all students’ potential regardless of gender;
- Introducing courses covering gender issues at all stages of the education system, supplemented with methodological materials;
- Developing a system to train qualified gender specialists to teach these courses.

Conclusion. Gender education should shape individuals capable of fulfilling the task of building a democratic society, creating a new Uzbekistan, and achieving the goals of the Third Renaissance. Education must equip both genders with the skills and knowledge to take active civic positions and lead constructive initiatives by deconstructing social stereotypes. Modern gender theory, while acknowledging biological, social, and psychological differences between the sexes, rejects deterministic links between anatomy and social roles. The introduction of gender education fosters gender equality in social relations and eliminates all forms of discrimination. It also creates the socio-political conditions and opportunities necessary for individuals to fully realize their natural abilities, regardless of gender.

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